

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PATHOGENETIC AXIS OF ORAL AND GUT MICROBIOMES UNDER THE TREATMENT OF PERIODONTAL LESION IN PATIENTS WITH NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE

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Abstract

NAFLD is also characterized by the formation of a pathogenetic axis between the oral and intestinal microbiomes. *Materials and methods.* The main group consisted of 44 patients with NAFLD, control group - 20 healthy patients. Clinical dental examination, determination of intestinal microbiota and periodontal pathogens was performed according 1 visit, after 7 days and after 3 months. The levels of gingipain-K and endotoxin in the oral fluid were determined at visits 1 and 3. *Results.* In the intestinal microbiome in NAFLD, the Firmicutes phylotype prevailed over Bacteroides. The level of *P. gingivalis* & *T. forsythia* was significantly higher in the study group. The level of gingipain-K was 24 times higher, and the level of oral fluid LPS was 2 times higher when compared with the control group. *Conclusions.* The tendency towards oral symbiosis is an important component of the comprehensive treatment of comorbid pathology.

Keywords: dysbiosis, metabolic-associated diseases, cavity microbiota, periodontitis.

The oral cavity, as the first part of the digestive system, is in direct contact with the external environment and is constantly under the influence of a spectrum of various exogenous risk factors. However, the healthy human body, in general, contributes to the absence of clinical manifestations of irreversible dental pathology [1]. The healthy periodontium has a sufficient level of adaptation to the constant action of exogenous risk factors, which, under certain conditions, contribute to the inflammatory-destructive process initiation. The decrease in the adaptive paradental capabilities occurs against the background of somatic pathology considered as an endogenous risk factor [2].

The special attention is recently given to metabolic-associated diseases, primarily non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) [3]. The change in the metabolic rate in NAFLD patients contributes to the phenomena of endogenous body intoxication negatively affecting the state of the periodontium [4]. Gut microbiome dysbiosis plays an important role in the initiation of many metabolic disorders (insulin resistance, obesity, type 2 diabetes mellitus, steatosis and steatohepatitis of the liver, cardiovascular pathology, etc.). The healthy gut microbiome is a guarantee of preventing any toxic metabolites penetration into the internal environment, firstly, in the absence of their formation, and secondly, due to their neutralization by symbiotic microorganisms [5,6]. However, dysbiosis in the gut microbiome structure contributes to the formation of excess concentrations of certain substances, metabolites, and such compounds absent in a healthy state. In addition, against the background of dysbiosis, a decrease in the detoxification microbiome capabilities and an increase in intestinal permeability take place contributing to endogenous body intoxication [7]. Therefore, the formation of a modern view of metabolic diseases as the pathogenetic axis formation is not accidental, for NAFLD it is the axis between the gut microbiome and the liver.

At the same time, the digestive system is characterized by the presence of another local microbiome inhabiting the oral cavity, the condition of which affects both the NAFLD course and its treatment efficacy [8]. That is, the pathogenetic axis formation between the oral cavity and gut microbiomes is characteristic of the NAFLD.

The oral cavity microbiota translocation into the intestines takes place constantly both in a healthy state and in the case of visceral diseases. As a result of saliva swallowing or food intake, oral resident microorganisms and their metabolites move to the lower gastrointestinal tract, but physiological physical (distance) and chemical (hydrochloric acid, bile) barriers stand in the way [9]. In the case of NAFLD, the barrier function against the background of metabolic disorders is reduced, and virulent oral microflora penetrates into the intestines and supports dysbiosis. The local effect of oral dysbiosis is inflammatory-destructive dental pathology – chronic periodontitis (CP). Specific periodontopathogenic microorganisms have a wide range of virulence factors, the activity of which is increased in the case of oral dysbiosis. Thus, *Porphyromonas gingivalis* (*P. gingivalis*), *Tanarella forsythia* (*T. forsythia*), *Treponema denticola* (*T. denticola*) are considered to be the most aggressive periodontopathogens, the infectivity and invasion of which increase with the CP progression [10]. Periodontopathogens from the oral CP focus penetrates directly into the gut biotope and into the systemic circulation and liver through the mucous membrane, supporting chronic systemic inflammation. Furthermore, dysbiotic oral microflora, as a result of invasion into the periodontium, penetrates into the bloodstream and indirectly into the liver, bypassing the intestines, through the portal pathway.

The research **objective** is to determine the level of aggressive periodontopathogens in NAFLD patients and its subsequent monitoring in the process of complex comorbid pathology treatment.

Materials and methods

The research is carried out with due regard to safety measures for the patient's health, compliance with his/her rights, human dignity and moral-and-ethical norms in accordance with the principles of the Helsinki Declaration of Human Rights, the Convention on Human Rights and the Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine, the Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences, the International Code of Medical Ethics and relevant legal acts regulating the clinical research.

44 patients with a confirmed NAFLD diagnosis participated in the research, the average age in the group was 46.79 ± 0.66 years old (male to female ratio 63.6%: 36.4%). The control group included 20 somatically healthy patients being representative by gender and age (55% of men). The NAFLD verification was carried out by a gastroenterologist in accordance with international and domestic criteria and recommendations (determination of anthropometric indicators taking into account past medical history, clinical and biochemical blood tests with determination of different-density lipoprotein cholesterol, triglycerides, total protein, albumin, liver function test, carbohydrate metabolism; ultrasound examination of the liver, elastography, steatography and liver steatometry) [11]. Clinical dental examination has been conducted three times (1 visit, in 7 days and in 3 months) according to the established procedure. A questionnaire has been conducted regarding the main dental complaints, attitude to the consumption of sweets, and the discipline as to the individual oral hygiene has also been determined. The dental examination included an index assessment of the hygiene level and the periodontium state, X-ray data and computer tomography data have been studied. Clinical attachment loss (CAL), probing depth and bleeding during probing, simplified oral hygiene index have been determined. The clinical attachment level of each segment has been recorded by adding the probing pocket depth and gingival recession measurements. Periodontitis was diagnosed based on the results of the 2017 World Workshop on the Classification of Periodontal and Peri-implant Diseases and Conditions [12].

Determination of gut microbiota and periodontopathogens has been carried out during the 1st and 3rd visit (immediately and 3 months after treatment). The gut microbiota composition has been studied at the main phylotypes level through identification of total bacterial DNA and DNA of Bacteroidetes, Firmicutes and Actinobacteria by quantitative PCR qRT-PCR using universal primers for the 16S rRNA gene and taxon-specific primers. In order to determine the level of periodontopathogens, the sampling from periodontal pockets has been carried out using paper endodontic absorbers, which were left in the pockets for 15-20 seconds in observance of minimal contact with atmospheric air, after which they were immediately transferred to separate Eppendorf-type tubes containing the reagent for further determination of the quantitative composition by the method of polymerase chain reaction (PCR) in real time (qRT-PCR) using universal primers.

The level of gingipain K and endotoxin (LPS) in the oral fluid has also been determined during the 1st

and 3rd visits using the immunoenzyme method. The "HUMAN GINGIPAIN K (KGP) ELISA KIT" (DRG Instruments GmbH, Germany) has been used in order to determine the gingipain K concentration. The concentration determination range is 15.6-2000.00 pg/ml; sensitivity 15.6 pg/ml. The determination of bacterial endotoxin concentration in saliva was carried out using the LAL Chromogenic Endpoint Assay kit (Hycult Biotech, the Netherlands). The concentration detection range is from 0.01 to 10 U/ml, sensitivity – 0.01 U ET/ml.

All patients received drug and non-drug treatment (dietary intervention, physical activity recommendations) of the NAFLD and insulin resistance. Additionally, patients received a probiotic in capsules containing 2 billion active cells (colony-forming units (CFU)) of *L. acidophilus*, *L. rhamnosus*, *Streptococcus salivarius* subsp. *thermophilus*, *L. delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus*) orally 1 capsule three times a day during meals for 12 weeks.

Dental treatment consisted of several stages. Thus, during the first visit, patients underwent the plaque disclosing and professional oral hygiene (removal of dental deposits, fabrication of individual dental splints for application of gels with chlorhexidine bigluconate for a period of 7 days). Each patient was motivated during conversation as to the dental health support, an individual algorithm for home oral cavity care has been developed (teeth cleaning methods, items and hygiene products have been selected). In appropriate cases, the gum care mousse containing probiotics was recommended to some patients as part of their home oral hygiene. In a week, the control examination was conducted in order to determine the discipline of patients with regard to the hygienic care and the hygienic index has been determined. During this visit, the second treatment stage has been initiated. Thus, the movable teeth splinting was carried out in appropriate cases, traumatic occlusion was eliminated. Patients with high level of periodontopathogens received oral bacteriophages and a probiotic for use with a soft dental split (12 weeks).

The SPSS Statistics data processing program package was used for statistical analysis. Data are presented in the form of median, interquartile range between the 25th and 75th percentiles (Me [Q1; Q3]). The Mann-Whitney U-test was used to assess intergroup quantitative differences, and the χ^2 test was used to compare a qualitative feature (detection frequency) in several groups. Detection of correlation between parameters was carried out using Spearman's analysis. For all types of analysis, differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Research results

All NAFLD patients had grade 1-2 obesity, as evidenced by a high body mass index (group mean = 32.2 [31.4; 37.4], while the examined patients from the control group had a body mass index within the normal range (22.4 [20.45; 24.1]). After the survey, it has been found that the main dental complaint of 77.3% of NAFLD patients was bleeding gums, of which 54.5% noted bleeding when brushing teeth, and 22.8% complained of bleeding during meals. When determining the usual lifestyle of these individuals, the prevalence

of bad habits was determined, namely the abuse of simple carbohydrates (88.6%) and smoking (45.45%), respectively. The complaint of bleeding gums when brushing teeth has also been observed in 20.0% in the control group, and the percentage of smoking patients was equal to 15.0% (Table 1).

The adequacy of home oral cavity care is an exclusively positive habit for periodontal health, however, its non-compliance was recorded only in patients of the main group. Only 59.1% of patients in the main group brushed their teeth twice a day, while the others considered brushing once in the morning to be sufficient. The number of patients in the control group who followed double cleaning was equal to 100%.

Table 1

Survey data of the main and control groups before treatment

Parameter	Main group (n=44)	Control group (n=20)
Bleeding gums (n,%)	34 (77.2%)*	4 (20.0%)
Smoking (n,%)	20 (45.45%)*	3 (15.0%)
Abuse of simple carbohydrates (n,%)	39 (88.6%)*	6 (30.0%)
Two-time teeth cleaning (n,%)	26 (59.1%)*	20 (100%)

Note: *-The difference is probable compared to the control group

The clinical oral dysbiosis sign was the chronic periodontitis (CP) of all degrees of severity in patients of the main group (Fig. 1). The clinical picture corresponded to the chronic inflammation state (bleeding gums and gingival tenderness, tooth mobility, in some

patients – exudation from periodontal pockets, bad breath, difficult food chewing). According to patients, these manifestations had a tendency to increase in recent years.

Fig. 1. Prevalence and structure of periodontal lesions among individuals of the studied groups before treatment

Note: *-The difference is probable compared to the control group

All periodontal tissue changes have been confirmed by specific dental indices characterizing the degree and spread of chronic inflammation in the periodontium, the depth of periodontal pockets, and the oral

hygiene level (Table 2). It should be added that the control group patients had chronic generalized catarrhal gingivitis (CGCG), which is explained by the home oral hygiene quality at the “satisfactory” level.

Table 2

Index evaluation of the periodontal of the main and control groups before treatment

Indicator	Main group	Control group	p
OHI-S, point	2.20 [1.80; 2.40]	1.40 [1.10;1.65]	0.001
PMA, %	25.43 [12.0; 27.7]	9.0 [5.50;13.00]	0.001
PBI, point	1.55 [0.00; 2.30]	0.2 [0.1;0.4]	0.001
Loss of attachment, mm	3.50 [0.00; 4.95]	0.16[0.07; 0.23]	0.001

The research results revealed that for the control group patients, the gut microbiome structure was characterized by the probable predominance of *Bacteroides* representatives over the *Firmicutes* phylotype. How-

ever, in the group of NAFLD patients, the gut microbiome was mostly inhabited by saccharolytic *Firmicutes* microflora, confirming the translocation of oral microorganisms to the intestines and the dysbiosis support (Table 3)

Table 3

Taxonomic composition of the intestinal microbiome of the main and control groups before treatment (LogU/ml)

Phylotype	Main group	Control group	p
Bacteroides	15.97 [8.55; 29.45]	34.65 [24.27; 44.23]	0.01
Firmicutes	49.66 [39.14; 60.39]	29.96 [22.27; 42.63]	0.01

The quantitative level of aggressive periodontopathogens was increased, and their pathogenicity increased in response to the CP course severity deterioration. The quantitative level of aggressive periodontopathogens is presented in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Level of some periodontopathogens in the studied groups before treatment

Patients of the main group had reliably higher levels of virulence factors in the oral fluid when compared to healthy patients. Thus, the average values of gingipain K in oral fluid in the main group were almost 24 times greater than the similar indicator in healthy patients (98.9 [84.2; 128.6] to 4.17 [2.85; 20.34] ($p=0.001$)), and the LPS concentration in the oral fluid of NAFLD patients exceeded that of healthy patients by almost 2 times ($p=0.006$).

A week after the professional oral hygiene, dental care training, and the fabrication of dental splints, an additional visit was conducted in order to determine the motivation of patients and hygienic care control (controlled teeth self-brushing). Thus, according to clinical data and OHI-S index data, the oral hygiene level improved compared to the 1st visit and became satisfactory ($p=0.001$). Without doubt, it is impossible to testify to the full oral cavity care normalization of patients due to the short period of time, especially after the removal of dental deposits. Mostly, the intermediate visit was carried out to monitor the patients' implementation of the prescribed algorithm and to answer some of the patients' questions.

In order to study the dynamics of pathological manifestations in the periodontium three months after the treatment initiation, a repeated set of studies was conducted – questionnaire, clinical examination of the

periodontium, study of the level of specific periodontopathogens and their virulence factors. In addition, possible changes in the gut microbiome structure have been determined. Thus, according to the results, after 12 weeks, not only the frequency of complaints as to the bleeding gums of patients in the main group decreased by almost half ($p=0.001$), but also the bleeding causes changed. Therefore, the majority of patients (31.8%) complained of bleeding when brushing teeth, and 11.36% suffered from bleeding during meals. Also, the number of patients with bad habits – abuse of simple carbohydrates and smoking – has significantly decreased. At the same time, adherence to brushing teeth twice a day was characteristic of a larger number of patients, but there was no significant increase in comparison with 1st visit.

The analysis of dental indices showed a decrease in the chronic inflammatory process intensity and bleeding gums. And although the OHI-S was 1.2 times lower than the indicator during the first visit, it showed an increase when compared to the 2nd visit. Clinically, 11 patients had signs of clinical chronic generalized periodontitis remission (absence of bleeding and painful gums, absence of exudation from periodontal pockets, decrease in tooth mobility). All clinical changes in the periodontium have been confirmed by periodontal indices (Table 4).

Table 4

Change in index assessment of periodontal disease in patients of the main group			
Indicator	1 st visit	3 rd visit	p
PMA, %	25.43 [12.0; 27.7]	15,50 [8.00; 25.00]	0.000
PBI, point	1.55 [0.00; 2.30]	1,15 [0.00; 1.82]	0.000
Loss of attachment, mm	3.50 [0.00; 4.95]	3,06 [0.00; 4.50]	

The creation of favorable background for CP regression in NAFLD patients was marked by a decrease in the quantitative level of aggressive periodontopathogens and their virulence factors. Thus, the reduction of attachment loss was positively correlated with the

quantitative level of periodontopathogenic microorganisms ($r=0.646$; $p=0.051$). (Fig. 3).

In addition, a significant double decrease in the level of gingipain K and LPS has been noted, confirming the CP regression and contributing to the reduction of negative impact on the gut microbiome.

Fig. 3. Positive changes in the quantitative level of aggressive periodontopathogens after treatment

The positive changes in the level of aggressive periodontopathogens contributed to the improvement of the taxonomic gut microbiome composition, constituting an important component in the NAFLD treatment. Before treatment in the group of NAFLD patients, the gut microbiota state was at the level of the main ones with the predominance of Firmicutes with a reciprocal Bacteroidetes decrease. In 3 months, an increase in the number of Bacteroides phylotypes was observed in the gut microbiome structure of patients from the main group compared to the 1st visit.

Discussion

The healthy state of physiological barriers promotes and maintains taxonomic divergence between the oral and gut microbiomes [13]. *Firmicutes* phylotype prevails in the oral cavity, and *Bacteroides* prevails in the intestines. The research results revealed that the probable predominance of *Bacteroides* representatives over the *Firmicutes* phylotype was characteristic of the gut microbiome structure for the control group patients. However, in the group of NAFLD patients, the gut microbiome was mostly inhabited by *Firmicutes* saccharolytic microflora, which confirmed the translocation of oral microorganisms to the intestines and dysbiosis support.

The above-mentioned data demonstrate the penetration of oral microorganisms from the CP focus into the gut microbiome, due to the reduction of barrier function against the background of NAFLD, and the dysbiosis support [14]. Such microorganisms have pronounced virulence factors directly causing the destruction of periodontal tissues, contributing to microbial invasion. One of these factors is a specific proteinase –

gingipain K produced by *P. Gingivalis* [15]. Other virulence factors have the ability to provoke the immune system, initiating a chronic inflammatory process contributing to the mediated destruction of the periodontium. Thus, the endotoxin-lipopolysaccharide (LPS) of the outer membrane of periodontopathogens has a sufficiently high immunogenicity. In addition, as the CP severity worsened, the quantitative level of aggressive periodontopathogens and the specified virulence factors (gingipain K/LPS) increased in the oral fluid [16].

This fact is reliable because when the CP course worsens, more favorable conditions are created (chronic inflammation, increased depth of periodontal pockets, hypoxia, increased permeability of epithelial cells, etc.) for further infectivity and invasion of aggressive periodontopathogens [17].

The CP treatment against the background of NAFLD sets, first of all, the goal of breaking the pathogenetic “vicious circle”, being the basis of comorbid pathology. This approach will contribute to positive changes in the long-term NAFLD treatment, which in turn has a positive effect on periodontal tissues, contributing to the CP regression and supporting stabilization [18]. Due to the dental treatment of CP, conditions for reduction of quantitative level and aggressiveness of periodontopathogenic microflora are created in the oral cavity.

The very first stage in the treatment of dental manifestations of NAFLD should be teaching the patient adequate oral hygiene at home. Maintaining proper hygiene is a necessary and important component of complex comorbid pathology treatment. All patients need periodic motivation and control of home hygiene in or-

der to maintain dental health. This fact confirms the results of our research, when, after hygiene classes, we observed an OHI-S improvement. However, in 3 months, the specified index worsened again, which we associate with a decrease in motivation to adequate oral hygiene at home. Therefore, most likely, patients with low motivation should be classified as a risk group and need increased attention (more frequent visits than 1 time in three months in order to form a stable habit).

Nevertheless, the 3rd visit made it possible to record a decrease in the activity of chronic inflammation in the periodontium and, especially, a decrease in the depth of periodontal pockets, being the ecological niches for infectivity of aggressive periodontopathogens. This fact indicates the normalization of pro-inflammatory immune system activity against the background of positive changes in the oral microbiome structure. The tendency to normalize the oral microbiome significantly reduces the negative impact on such gut microbiome structure, increasing the sensitivity to NAFLD therapy [19]. Thus, statistics indicate that the number of Firmicutes decreased significantly and the content of Bacteroidetes increased in patients of the main group, although the changes did not reach the GM indicators in the control group. The obtained data prove the ability of the additional prescription of probiotics to regulate both gut and oral microbiota.

It should be noted that the period of NAFLD therapy is long, but in order to determine the positive changes, the specified period is sufficient, due to the adaptive capabilities of the periodontium and the direct influence on the risk factors for the comorbid pathology initiation.

Conclusions

The oral microbiome dysbiosis is clinically confirmed by the CP occurrence, especially against the background of NAFLD.

Aggressive periodontopathogens and their virulence factors negatively affect the gut microbiome and support dysbiosis in its structure.

The tendency to oral symbiosis against the background of NAFLD is an important component of the complex comorbid pathology therapy, aimed at breaking the pathogenetic “vicious circle” and normalizing the relationship along the “oral microbiome-gut microbiome” axis.

Ethics. This study was approved by the Clinical Research Ethics Committee of the Government Institution “L.T. Malaya Therapy National Institute of the National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine. The study was carried out in accordance with the ethical rules of the Declaration of Helsinki

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